

IMPACT OF A STRESS MANAGEMENT EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF UNDERGRADUATE NURSING STUDENTS

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Abstract

*Background: Nursing students experience high levels of stress due to academic and clinical demands, which negatively affect psychological well-being and academic performance. Stress management interventions have been shown to improve coping abilities, resilience, and learning outcomes, yet evidence from Pakistan remains limited. Aim: The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of a structured stress management educational program on psychological well-being and academic achievement among undergraduate nursing students in Swat. Methods: A quasi-experimental study design was used. The sample size of 54 undergraduate nursing students was calculated using the G*Power calculator. Participants were recruited purposively from different nursing colleges in Swat. Data were collected in three phases: pre-intervention, intervention, and post-intervention. The intervention consisted of a four-week program that included sessions on relaxation techniques, time management, coping strategies, and mindfulness practices. Data were analyzed using SPSS, with paired sample t-tests applied to compare pre- and post-intervention scores. Results: The majority of participants were male (93%). Post-intervention results indicated a significant reduction in stress scores ($p < 0.001$) and a significant improvement in psychological well-being ($p < 0.001$). Academic performance scores also improved significantly following the intervention ($p < 0.001$). Chi-square analysis revealed no significant association between year of study and post-intervention stress levels ($p > 0.05$). Conclusion: The stress management educational program was effective in reducing stress, enhancing psychological well-being, and improving academic achievement among nursing students. Integrating such programs into nursing curricula may strengthen student resilience and academic outcomes.*

INTRODUCTION

The effect of perceived excessive demands on coping capabilities is the body's reaction to the situation, which leads to stress, particularly prevalent among

students in high-demanding academic programs (Hamadi et al., 2021). The strategies of stress management include relaxation, time management,

and coping skills, which should be used to decrease the level of stress and enhance functioning (Mitchell, 2023). Mental health balance is described as psychological well-being and encompasses several aspects, including resilience, self-care, and positive emotions (du Plessis, 2025). The most common measures of academic achievement are the performance of the students in tests, grades, and evaluations (Kumar et al., 2021). The stress levels among undergraduate nursing students are especially susceptible to stress compared to other groups of students because of academic and clinical pressures (Chaabane et al., 2021).

Nursing students have been reported to experience stress with moderate to severe levels across the world (Zheng et al., 2022). Research in Asia and Middle Eastern countries confirms stress prevalence, and over half of nursing students are under a psychological burden during their educational program (Chaabane et al., 2021). To support this claim, recent studies in Pakistan have found that as many as 65 percent of undergraduate nursing students report experiencing academic-related stress, which leads to anxiety and depression (Bibi et al., 2024). It is found that stress contributes to absenteeism, poor academic performance, and increased rates of dropout in nursing education (Khan et al., 2023). This prevalence highlights the acute necessity of the interventions aimed at the promotion of coping and psychological well-being (Adu, 2023).

Nursing education implies intensive coursework, mastering of skills and practical work, which considerably raise stress levels (Mazalova et al., 2022). The students are frequently exposed to acutely sick patients, emergency care, and long working hours, which may enhance the burden of psychology (Glick et al., 2024). The necessity to fulfill the academic necessities and engage in clinical placements adds additional stress to nursing students (Dogham et al., 2024). It is also reported that nursing students often have role overload because of various responsibilities (Aryuwat et al., 2024). In the absence of proper support, several individuals will find it challenging to be effective in academics and clinical learning (Falloon et al., 2023).

Nursing students experience adverse effects of high stress on the psychological well-being (Fauzi et al.,

2021). The most frequent are fatigue, irritability, sleeping disorders, and low concentration, which disrupt academic and clinical performance (Poorhosseini Dehkordi, 2023). Stress raised the chance of experiencing depression, anxiety, and burnout prior to becoming a professional (Selvakumar et al., 2026). Unmanaged stress is a factor that students frequently report to have low motivation, reduced confidence, and reduced self-care (Jeyasingh, 2022). Ineffective well-being in training is a determining factor in the long-term effects of both individual well-being and the quality of the nursing staff (Chaabane et al., 2021).

Academic achievement in nursing education is a powerful factor affected by stress (Dogham et al., 2024). Chronic stress affects the mental functions like memory, selection of decisions and problem solving (Alhasani and Orji, 2025). It has been indicated that stressed student nurses are not successful in examinations and clinical assessments (Bibi et al., 2024). Academic stress is also the cause of disappointment in the study programs and low skill acquisition (Khan et al., 2023). Stress is one of the factors that directly affect academic performance when uncontrolled and eventually the competence of the future nursing practitioners (Adu, 2023).

Stress management interventions in the form of education have shown beneficial outcomes in the well-being of nursing students (Hamadi et al., 2021). Mindfulness, resilience training and coping skills workshops are types of programs that benefit students in terms of psychological health and academic performance (Mitchell, 2023). Researchers point out that structured interventions have a strong impact on stress levels and a positive effect on coping (van der Riet et al., 2015; replaced by Aryuwat et al., 2024). Time management training and a facilitating mobile application have recorded encouraging results in enhancing coping and academic results (Alhasani & Orji, 2025). In addition to improving empathy, resilience, and professional confidence, stress management interventions also have a connection (Selvakumar et al., 2026).

In Pakistan, there is little on the structured stress management intervention among nursing students (Bibi et al., 2024). The increase in the level of academic stress in the local nursing institutions underlines the urgency of the systematic strategies

adoption (Khan et al., 2023). Although the level of awareness is rising, the majority of institutions do not have formal programs to encourage coping and resilience (Adu, 2023). The experience of the adjacent countries indicates that specific educational activities can have a strong positive impact on psychological well-being and academic outcomes of nursing students (Chaabane et al., 2021). The assessment of the effect of the stress management educational interventions in Pakistan will be used to fill in the major knowledge gaps and inform the nursing education reforms (Hamadi et al., 2021).

Methodology

The study employed a quasi-experimental design to examine the impact of an educational intervention on stress management, psychological well-being, and academic achievement of undergraduate nursing students. It was conducted in different nursing colleges located in Swat, Pakistan. The target population consisted of BSN students, and the sample size was calculated using the G*Power calculator, which indicated a minimum of 54 participants. Purposive sampling was applied to recruit eligible students based on inclusion criteria. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board, and written informed consent was secured. Participation was voluntary, and confidentiality was maintained.

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected in three phases. In the pre-intervention phase, baseline information was obtained using a structured questionnaire that measured stress, psychological well-being, and academic performance. The tool was validated by an expert nursing panel (CVI 0.92) and demonstrated reliability through Cronbach's alpha testing (Cronbach's alpha 0.86). In the intervention phase, participants received a structured stress management educational program developed by the researchers. The program included sessions on relaxation techniques, time management, coping skills, and mindfulness, delivered once a week for four weeks, with each session lasting 60–90 minutes. In the post-intervention phase, data were collected one month later using the same questionnaire to evaluate

changes in knowledge, stress levels, and academic outcomes.

Interventional Protocols

The intervention consisted of a structured **stress management educational program** designed by the researchers to enhance psychological well-being and academic performance among undergraduate nursing students. The program was implemented over a period of four weeks through weekly face-to-face sessions lasting 60–90 minutes. Each session included lectures, group discussions, role play, and demonstrations focusing on relaxation techniques, time management, coping strategies, and mindfulness practices. Participants were divided into small groups to encourage active participation and peer learning. Supplementary reading materials and self-practice exercises were provided at the end of each session. Attendance was monitored, and participants were encouraged to apply the techniques in both academic and clinical settings.

Data Analysis Procedure

The collected data were coded and entered into SPSS for analysis. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize demographic characteristics and baseline findings. Paired sample t-tests were applied to compare pre- and post-intervention scores for stress, psychological well-being, and academic performance. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

Results and Analysis

The demographic analysis showed that most participants were male (93%), while only a small proportion were female (7%). The majority of students were aged 21–23 years (53.7%), followed by 18–20 years (27.8%) and 24 years and above (18.5%). Regarding academic year, 29.6% were in 2nd year, 27.8% in 3rd year, 22.2% in 1st year, and 20.4% in 4th year. This indicates that the sample was predominantly male, in early adulthood, and fairly distributed across different academic years.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Nursing Students (N = 54)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	50	93
Female	4	7
Age (years)		
18-20	15	27.8
21-23	29	53.7
24 and above	10	18.5
Year of Study		
1st Year	12	22.2
2nd Year	16	29.6

3rd Year	15	27.8
4th Year	11	20.4

The results showed a significant reduction in stress scores from a pre-test mean of 28.4 ± 5.6 to a post-test mean of 20.2 ± 4.8 ($t = 8.21, p < 0.001$). Psychological well-being improved significantly, increasing from a pre-test mean of 32.6 ± 6.2 to a post-test mean of 40.7 ± 5.9 ($t = -7.84, p < 0.001$). These findings indicate that the educational intervention was effective in reducing stress and enhancing psychological well-being among nursing students.

Table 2. Comparison of Stress and Psychological Well-being Scores Before and After Intervention (N = 54)

Variable	Pre-test Mean \pm SD	Post-test Mean \pm SD	t-value	p-value
Stress Score	28.4 ± 5.6	20.2 ± 4.8	8.21	<0.001
Psychological Well-being	32.6 ± 6.2	40.7 ± 5.9	-7.84	<0.001

The findings revealed a significant improvement in academic achievement following the intervention. The mean score increased from 65.3 ± 7.1 in the pre-test to 74.5 ± 6.4 in the post-test ($t = -6.92, p < 0.001$). This indicates that the stress management educational program had a positive impact on students' academic performance.

Table 3. Academic Performance Scores Before and After Intervention (N = 54)

Variable	Pre-test Mean \pm SD	Post-test Mean \pm SD	t-value	p-value
Academic Achievement Score	65.3 ± 7.1	74.5 ± 6.4	-6.92	<0.001

The Chi-square test revealed no significant association between year of study and post-intervention stress levels ($\chi^2 = 1.74, df = 6, p = 0.94$). Across all academic years, the majority of students reported low stress (61.1%), followed by moderate stress (31.5%), while only a small proportion experienced high stress (7.4%). This suggests that the educational intervention was effective in reducing stress consistently among students, regardless of their year of study.

Table 4. Association Between Year of Study and Post-intervention Stress Level (N = 54)

Year of Study	Low Stress n (%)	Moderate Stress n (%)	High Stress n (%)	χ^2	df	p-value
1st Year (n=12)	7 (58.3)	4 (33.3)	1 (8.4)			
2nd Year (n=16)	10 (62.5)	5 (31.3)	1 (6.2)			
3rd Year (n=15)	9 (60.0)	5 (33.3)	1 (6.7)	1.74	6	0.94
4th Year (n=11)	7 (63.6)	3 (27.3)	1 (9.1)			
Total	33 (61.1)	17 (31.5)	4 (7.4)			

Discussion

The current research determined the effect of a stress management educational program on the psychological and academic success of undergraduate nursing students. Results showed that most of the participants were male (93%), which is the gender

composition in the nursing institutions in Swat. The intervention reflected a notable decrease in levels of stress, improvement of the psychological well-being, and improvements in academic performance. These findings indicate the significance of the structured educational interventions in solving psychological

difficulties in which nursing students undergo in both academic and clinical training.

The large reduction of stress scores following the intervention is in line with the results of Haver et al. (2025), who stated that resilience and stress reduction in the presented nursing students were significantly enhanced by stress management training and improving emotional intelligence. Equally, as noted by Berdida et al. (2023), psychological well-being and regulation of stress was reinforced through mindfulness and coping strategies. Conversely, Cohen et al. (2023) established that in certain healthcare settings, stress levels were elevated despite workplace interventions, which are designed to reduce stress levels, which is why institutional and resource disparities may have a role in the success of such programs.

Improvement in the psychological well-being in this study is also consistent with the findings reported by Berdida et al. (2023), who established that resilience, mindfulness and self efficacy had a significant positive impact on the outcomes of mental health among nursing students. Moreover, the researchers Worsley et al. (2022) came to the conclusion that evidence-based interventions positively improved the well-being of students in higher education, and this conclusion supports the results of the current study. Nonetheless, Agyapong et al. (2023) also highlighted that there may be an insufficient benefit of interventions in the long term due to the continuous workload requirements, which is consistent with the fact that sustained institutional assistance is needed in the context of the short-term training.

The level of academic performance greatly increased after the intervention, as Jaramillo Gomez et al. (2025) also noted a positive effect of critical thinking and coping strategies on learning results in higher education. On the same note, Haver et al. (2025) proposed that training on emotional intelligence enhances psychological well-being and academic performance. However, Hussain et al. (2025) also demonstrated that external stressors, including ethical dilemmas and systemic challenges can prevent the transfer of the psychological gains to academic achievements, which underscores the importance of extending academic support systems.

Correlation analysis in the present study showed that the year of study and post-intervention stress levels

were not significantly related to each other, which is contrary to higher stress scores in senior students as indicated by Mazalova et al. (2022) because of more clinical duties. Such a difference can be attributed to the fact that the intervention used in the current study was organized in groups and therefore offered an equivalent amount of support to all academic years, which minimized the difference in stress levels between cohorts.

The outcomes also highlight the wider scope of the application of stress management in the nursing programs. Worsley et al. (2022) reasoned that higher educational institutions do not have social structures designed to help students, which increases the level of stress. The results of the current study indicate that the given gap can be filled with the help of the designed educational programs and the improvement of psychological health and academic performance. The comparisons with the work of other researchers prove that the intervention strategies vary: they can be mindfulness or resilience training, but the results consistently show better mental health and academic performance (Berdida et al., 2023; Haver et al., 2025).

All in all, the results suggest that stress management interventions are feasible and justified in nursing education, and in the environment with limited resources, like Swat. The findings resonate with the evidence in the world and fill local practice gaps. Nevertheless, there are issues to be overcome like sustainability, institutional commitment, and integration of stress management within formal curricula. The long-term follow-up studies should be incorporated in the future research to estimate the sustainability of the intervention and to examine other two variables including gender differences, clinical workload, and systemic support that can possibly affect outcomes.

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that a structured stress management educational program significantly reduced stress levels, improved psychological well-being, and enhanced academic performance among undergraduate nursing students in Swat. The findings highlight the effectiveness of targeted interventions in addressing the psychological and academic challenges commonly faced by nursing

students. The results are consistent with international evidence showing that stress management strategies not only improve mental health but also positively influence learning outcomes. The study emphasizes the need to integrate stress management into nursing education to better prepare students for academic and clinical demands.

Recommendations

1. Nursing colleges should incorporate structured stress management programs into their curricula as part of ongoing student support and professional development.
2. Regular workshops on mindfulness, relaxation techniques, time management, and coping skills should be organized to sustain psychological well-being among nursing students.
3. Faculty and administrators should establish counseling and peer-support systems to provide continuous emotional and academic assistance.
4. Long-term follow-up studies are recommended to assess the sustained impact of stress management interventions on both academic performance and clinical competence.
5. Policymakers and educational authorities should prioritize the development of student wellness policies that include structured mental health interventions in nursing institutions.
6. Future research should compare the effectiveness of different intervention models, such as digital programs versus face-to-face workshops, to identify the most feasible approaches in resource-limited contexts.

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